

Triflumizole encapsulation by 2-hydroxypropyl and sulphated derivatives of β -cyclodextrin

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Abstract : Spectroscopic studies were done on the inclusion of triflumizole (TF) into the cavities of two derivatives of β -cyclodextrin namely hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (HP- β -CD) and sulphated- β -cyclodextrin (S- β -CD). The affinity of TF for the cavities of cyclodextrin derivatives was found to be dependent on the interaction forces responsible for complexation. Solubility enhancement of TF by HP- β -CD and S- β -CD has been explained using a thermodynamic approach. Calculations of the thermodynamic parameters showed that the inclusion reaction was favored by entropy-enthalpy compensation phenomenon. Phase solubility studies showed that both the inclusion complexes were of A type indicating enhancement of the solubility of TF molecule upon encapsulation.

Keywords : Hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin, inclusion complexes, solubility, sulphated- β -cyclodextrin, triflumizole.

Introduction

Encapsulation of pesticides (fungicides, herbicides, etc.) with cyclodextrins (CDs) results in an advantageous modifications of their properties like enhanced solubility and therefore, a better activity and bioavailability, leading to more efficient application. Triflumizole (TF) (Fig. 1(a)) is a fungicidal compound with systemic effect against plant mycosis like powdery mildew, rust and scab on cereals, arboricultures and vinicultures. The saturation concentration of this compound in pure water is very low and thus standard formulations are usually applied as suspension concentrates¹. A possible method providing solubility enhancement seems to be due to the inclusion of the compound by convenient molecules like CDs². CDs are cyclic oligo saccharides made of six, seven, or eight (for α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin respectively) glucopyranose units bound by α -1,4-ether linkages containing a hydrophobic central cavity and a hydrophilic outer surface. CDs can host a large number of organic molecules with low aqueous solubility by non covalent interaction forces³ leading to an increase of aqueous solubility and stability of these organic molecules⁴.

Solubilising effect of CDs is of particular interest in the pharmaceutical industry and chemical technology. Enhancement of the solubility of drugs or pesticides, con-

ferring subsequent bioavailability and improved activity, is caused by complexation of the hydrophobic compounds with appropriate host molecules. Because of the variability in size of the interior cavity, association complexes of CDs have been widely studied. The stability of the inclusion complexes is determined by the fit of the molecular shape of the guest molecule to the molecular surface of the cavity, attractive van der Waals and electrostatic forces, as well as interaction with the environment¹. Though, there have been few studies on increase in the solubility of TF by β -cyclodextrin (β -CD)^{2,5} but there is very limited or practically no information on the solubility enhancement of TF by derivatives of β -CD such as 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (HP- β -CD) (Fig. 1(b)) and β -cyclodextrin-sulphated sodium salt (S- β -CD) (Fig. 1(c)). Moreover, HP- β -CD has attracted growing interest due to its improved complexing ability, greater water solubility and less toxicity⁶. Also, the types of interactions existing between these two derivatives of β -CD and TF are seldom reported.

In this article, we have investigated the ability of TF to form inclusion complexes with HP- β -CD and S- β -CD, in order to evaluate their effect on TF solubility in aqueous phase. Phase solubility studies at various temperatures were carried out to find the thermodynamic param-

eters of inclusion phenomenon. The binding behaviour of HP- β -CD and S- β -CD with the TF molecule were investigated by UV-Visible spectrometry. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and powder X-ray diffraction methods were used to characterize the inclusion complexes formed.

Fig. 1. Molecular structures of (a) TF, (b) HP- β -CD and (c) S- β -CD.

Experimental

Materials and experimental methods :

TF (guest) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., USA. HP- β -CD and S- β -CD (hosts) were also provided by Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., USA. The other reagents used as buffer (sodium phosphate, sodium acetate, sodium carbonate and sodium chloride) were supplied by Qualigens, India (Mumbai) and were of analytical grade.

Instrumental studies :

The UV-Visible (UV-Vis) spectra were recorded with a Lambda 25 UV/Vis, Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis spectrometer using quartz cells, between 200 and 400 nm. In the experiments of guest with hosts, the concentrations of the hosts were varied from 1×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ to 5×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ while the concentration of the guest was kept constant at 1.73×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹. The mixtures were stirred at 25 °C at a speed of 280 rpm for 4 h and the supernatant was analyzed by UV-Vis spectrometer. Powder X-ray diffraction spectrum was taken by Bruker D2 Phaser diffractometer. FTIR spectra were obtained by the KBr method using Perkin-Elmer, model Spectrum

One.

Solubility experiment :

Solubility measurements and the determination of the saturation concentrations were carried out by adding excess amount of the TF to different concentrations of HP- β -CD and S- β -CD aqueous solutions. The samples were

stirred (280 rpm) in a temperature controlled water bath until equilibrium was reached. Then the solution was centrifuged and supernatant liquid was removed and diluted with buffer solution (pH 7). The concentration of TF thus obtained was determined by UV-Vis spectrometer. The saturation concentrations were determined at different temperatures, i.e. 25 °C, 35 °C and 45 °C and at a constant pH of 7.

Synthesis of inclusion complexes :

The guest and the hosts were fully dissolved in phosphate buffer (pH 7) at a molar ratio 1 : 1 and then the two solutions were mixed and stirred at 25 °C for 24 h. Dried complexes were obtained by lyophilisation in a freeze dryer where samples were frozen at -49 °C for 6 h followed by drying at 0.002 mbar for 12 h. The powders obtained were stored in gas-tight bottles at -20 °C until further analysis.

Results and discussion

UV-Visible analysis :

Evidence of intermolecular interaction between TF with HP- β -CD and S- β -CD in aqueous solution (at pH 7) at 298 K could be gained from UV-Vis study. Fig. 2

Fig. 2. UV absorption spectra of TF ($1.73 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) in presence of (a) HP- β -CD and (b) S- β -CD. The concentrations of the hosts are in the range 1 to $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.

(a and b) shows the UV-Vis spectrum of TF with HP- β -CD and S- β -CD, respectively. The absorption spectrum of free TF showed bands with maxima at 223 nm and 276 nm, respectively. In case of the system of TF with HP- β -CD, even though the changes in wavelength corresponding to the positions of the bands were marginal, but the absorption intensity decreased with increasing concentra-

tion of HP- β -CD showing that TF was experiencing a less polar environment with increasing concentration of HP- β -CD. Considering that the cavity of HP- β -CD was a less polar micro-environment than aqueous solution, the absorption result suggested the formation of HP- β -CD inclusion complex of TF from water to the cavity. Interestingly, upon complexation with S- β -CD three absorption bands appeared at 251 nm, 256 nm and 262 nm, and the intensity of the bands increased with increasing concentration of S- β -CD signifying that TF was experiencing a more polar micro-environment in the cavity of S- β -CD than aqueous solution⁷, thereby confirming the existence of an intermolecular interaction between TF molecule and S- β -CD.

In order to further study association behavior of TF with CDs, solid inclusion complexes of HP- β -CD and S- β -CD were prepared and characterized.

Phase solubility analysis :

The phase solubility technique allowed the evaluation of affinity between hosts and guest in aqueous phase. The solubility of TF was determined by increasing the amount of HP- β -CD and S- β -CD, varying from 0 to $6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ in a temperature range from 25 °C to 45 °C. The phase solubility profiles of complex formation between TF and hosts are shown in the Figs. 3 (a and b). An increase in the solubility of the TF with rising CDs concentration and ascending temperature was observed, indicating the solubilising ability of the host molecules. According to Higuchi and Connors⁸ classification, the phase solubility diagrams of both the HP- β -CD-TF and S- β -CD-TF inclusion complexes were of A type, which indicated the formation of soluble complexes. Apparent stability constant (K_{st}) of the inclusion complexes were calculated from the straight line of the phase solubility diagram by using eq. (1)⁹ :

$$K_{st} = \frac{\text{Slope}}{S_0(1 - \text{slope})} \quad (1)$$

where S_0 is the equilibrium solubility of TF in aqueous phase.

The stability constant value is a useful index to estimate the degree of binding strength of a complex. The K_{st} values obtained at 25 °C were within the range of 100–5000 M^{-1} , which is considered as adequate for the formation of stable inclusion complex and may contrib-

Fig. 3. Phase solubility diagram of (a) HP-β-CD-TF inclusion complex and (b) S-β-CD-TF inclusion complex at different temperatures at pH 7.

ute to the improvement of the fungicidal activity of the TF molecule¹⁰. The value of K_{st} for S-β-CD-TF was found to be higher than that of HP-β-CD-TF, which may be due to greater affinity of sulphated oxygen towards hydrogen bonding¹¹. The dependencies of $\ln K_{st}$ on the reciprocal temperatures (according to Van't Hoff equation) are given in Fig. 4; the corresponding thermodynamic values are depicted in Table 1. Typical Van't Hoff plots confirmed fairly well to the linear behaviour over the temperature range from 25 °C to 45 °C (Fig. 4). Thermodynamic parameters (Table 1) showed that the inclusion complex phenomenon for S-β-CD-TF was predominantly due to

Fig. 4. Van't Hoff plot of HP-β-CD-TF and S-β-CD-TF systems at 25°, 35° and 45 °C.

favourable enthalpy of reaction (ΔH_r) which could still compensate more for the unfavourable entropy of reaction (ΔS_r). In other words, negative ΔH_r value suggested that inclusion of TF into S-β-CD was an enthalpy driven process. While negative value of ΔS_r suggested that more water molecules were bound to the products than reactants¹². This indicated that, in this complex, S-β-CD, hydrophobic interactions were not the predominant factor for complex formation but rather other intermolecular forces such as hydrogen bonding, dipole-dipole interactions, etc. might be responsible¹⁰. The complexation of TF with S-β-CD showed an overall reaction enthalpy of $-25.66 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$ and the related reaction entropy was $-9.09 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$, which led to pronounced enthalpy-entropy compensation. In contrast, the enthalpy of the reaction with the more hydrophobic HP-β-CD was much smaller, even the association constant was quite large. The resulting reaction entropy was therefore positive, which implied that the entropy contributed to the increase in free reaction enthalpy and stability constant¹³. The reaction was, therefore, mainly entropy driven.

Powder X-ray diffraction spectrum (P-XRD) :

The formation of the inclusion complexes can be confirmed by X-ray diffractometry analysis¹⁴. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of HP-β-CD, S-β-CD and their inclusion complexes with the TF are shown in Figs. (5a-d). The 2θ values of the top peaks in the curve of hosts and the corresponding inclusion complexes in Fig. 5 are

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters of the overall complexation between S- β -CD and HP- β -CD with TF at 25 °C

Systems	K_{st} (mol L ⁻¹) ⁻¹	ΔG_r (KJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_r (KJ mol ⁻¹)	$T\Delta S_r$ (KJ mol ⁻¹)
S- β -CD-TF	806 \pm 0.02	-16.57 \pm 0.03	-25.66 \pm 0.05	-9.09 \pm 0.02
HP- β -CD-TF	667 \pm 0.01	-16.10 \pm 0.02	-3.95 \pm 0.01	+12.15 \pm 0.01

Fig. 5. Powder X-ray diffraction spectra of (a) HP- β -CD, (b) S- β -CD, (c) HP- β -CD-TF and (d) S- β -CD-TF.

listed in Table 2. HP- β -CD has two strong peaks at 8.09° and 18.46°, respectively. In contrast, HP- β -CD-TF complex showed disappearance of the characteristic peaks of HP- β -CD and formation of a diffused diffraction pattern. Moreover, the intensity of the peaks of HP- β -CD-TF also decreased to an enormous extent indicating a more amorphous character in the complex¹⁵. For the S- β -CD host, only one broad strong peak appeared at 21.8° whereas

two new strong peaks were observed in S- β -CD-TF at 23.3° and 31.72°, respectively and the intensities of the peaks rapidly increased, indicating a crystalline nature of the complex¹⁵. In addition, the diffraction peaks of S- β -CD became sharp after inclusion and also shifted to higher 2 θ value. The formation of a diffuse diffraction pattern, appearance of new peaks and disappearance of characteristic peaks were reported as evidence for formation of inclusion complex of guest with CDS^{17,18}.

Table 2. XRD data of the β -CD derivatives and their inclusion complexes with TF

Host	XRD peak 2 θ (deg)	Inclusion complex	XRD peak 2 θ (deg)
HP- β -CD	8.09	HP- β -CD-TF	8.70
	18.46		Peak disappeared
S- β -CD	21.86	S- β -CD-TF	23.32
			31.76 (new peak)

The clear differences between the XRD patterns of each host and their corresponding inclusion complexes suggested intermolecular interaction of TF with HP- β -CD and S- β -CD in the solid state.

FTIR analysis of inclusion complexes :

FTIR spectroscopy was used to characterize inclusion complex formation of TF molecule with the hosts. FTIR

spectra of free HP- β -CD showed strong absorption bands at 3395.39 cm^{-1} and 1650.41 cm^{-1} , attributing to free $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ vibrations of the aromatic ring. There were a series of bands at 500–1500 cm^{-1} , which were assigned to the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$ vibrations in the fingerprint region. The shift in the corresponding bands to 3559.53 cm^{-1} , 1643.74 cm^{-1} and change of bands in the fingerprint region of solid HP- β -CD-TF demonstrated inclusion of TF into HP- β -CD cavity.

FTIR spectra of free S- β -CD which displayed two strong absorption bands at 3372.60 cm^{-1} and 1647.11 cm^{-1} , corresponding to free $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ vibrations of the aromatic ring. Upon inclusion, these characteristic bands shifted to 3442.10 cm^{-1} and 1654.66 cm^{-1} , respectively. Also, a series of bands, which appeared at 650–1500 cm^{-1} in S- β -CD assigned to the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$ vibrations in the fingerprint region changed significantly in S- β -CD-TF.

In addition, the reduction in intensity of the $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ band in both the complexes gave substantiation that a part of the TF molecule is trapped by the cavity of the β -CD derivatives studied².

Conclusions

The complexation of TF with HP- β -CD and S- β -CD leads to a considerable enhancement of the solubility with increasing amount of CDs. The CDs studied herein, formed 1 : 1 complexes with TF. The stability constants obtained were considered as adequate for the formation of stable inclusion complexes, which may contribute to the improvement of bioavailability of TF. It is evident that the change of the microenvironment from the hydration shell in aqueous solution to the more hydrophobic interior of the host molecules is responsible for the modification of the molecular properties. For the two hosts investigated – the association with S- β -CD showed enthalpy-entropy compensation, whereas the reaction with HP- β -CD was supported by the reaction entropy. Powder-XRD and FTIR analysis also supported inclusion phenomenon.

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Nomenclature

K_{st}	= Apparent stability constant	$[(\text{mol L}^{-1})^{-1}]$
KJ	= Kilojoule	[–]
L	= Litre	[–]
M	= Molar	[–]
nm	= Nano meter	[–]
rpm	= Revolution per minute	[–]
ΔH_{r}	= Enthalpy of reaction	[KJ mol ⁻¹]
ΔG_{r}	= Free energy of reaction	[KJ mol ⁻¹]
ΔS_{r}	= Entropy of reaction	[KJ mol ⁻¹]
θ	= Diffraction angle	

References

1. CH. TH. Klein, G. Kohler, B. Mayer, K. Mraz, S. Reiter, H. Viernstein and P. Wolschann, *J. Inclusion Phenom. Mol. Recognit. Chem.*, 1995, **22**, 15.
2. H. Viernstein, S. Reiter and P. Wolschann, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1994, **125**, 681.
3. K. H. Fromming and J. Szejtli, "Cyclodextrins in Pharmacy", Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, 1994.
4. T. Loftsson and M. Brewster, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1996, **85**, 1017.
5. H. Viernstein, P. Weiss-Greiler and P. Wolschann, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2003, **256**, 85.
6. L. Szente and J. Szejtli, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.*, 1999, **36**, 17.
7. L. X. Song, H. M. Wang, Yang and Y. Yang, *Acta Chim. Sinica*, 2007, **65**, 1593.
8. T. Higuchi and K. A. Connors, *Adv. Anal. Chem. Instr.*, 1965, **4**, 117.
9. C. Nicolescu, C. Ararna, A. Nedelcu and C.-M. Monciu, *Farmacia*, 2010, **58**, 620.
10. G. S. Jadhav, A. R. Patel, P. R. Vavia, A. K. Malde and B. C. Coutinho, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, 2006, **56**, 261.
11. E. Wernersson, J. Heyda, A. Kubickova, P. Coufal and P. Jungwirth, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2010, **114**, 11934.
12. K. Uekarna, F. Hirayama and M. Otagiri, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1978, **26**, 1162.
13. S. Charurnanee, A. Titwan, J. Sirithunyalug, P. Weiss-Greiler, P. Wolschann, H. Viernstein and S. Okonogi, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.*, 2006, **81**, 523.
14. T. Pralhad and K. Rajendrakurnar, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2004, **34**, 333.
15. L. X. Song, H. M. Wang, X. Q. Guo and L. Bai, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 8305.
16. M. D. Veiga, P. J. Diaz and F. Ahsan, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1998, **87**, 891.
17. M. D. Veiga and F. Ahsan, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2000, **48**, 793.
18. C. M. Fernandes, V. M. Teresa and F. J. Veiga, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2002, **15**, 79.